

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH PROCESSES IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS.

Isakhanova Mohidil Erkinovna

Ko'konQDI, senior teacher.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11528229>

Abstract. This article describes the psychological features of the development of speech processes in elementary school students. The article emphasizes the role of the teacher in the development of the speech of elementary school students. The article reflects the author's scientific views on the elimination of speech defects of elementary school students. The author's recommendations on the development of speech culture and technique in students of this age have been given.

Key words: Elementary fluency, speech, speech disorder, development of speech culture and speech technique.

ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ РЕЧЕВЫХ ПРОЦЕССОВ У УЧАЩИХСЯ МЛАДШИХ КЛАССОВ.

Аннотация. В данной статье описаны психологические особенности развития речевых процессов у учащихся младших классов. В статье подчеркивается роль учителя в развитии речи учащихся младших классов. В статье отражены научные взгляды автора на устранение дефектов речи учащихся младших классов. Даны авторские рекомендации по развитию культуры и техники речи у учащихся этого возраста.

Ключевые слова: речь, речевые нарушения, развитие культуры и техника речи.

**"The main pillars of the new Uzbekistan
will be knowledge, education and training!"**

Sh.M. Mirziyoyev

Every person who connects the fate of the country with the future of the youngsters and realizes that their perspectives are the perspective of the country, first of all pays special attention to the issue of raising and educating the children of this country. Based on this law, it is not for nothing that the leader of our country is raising education to the level of politics. At the same time, one of the main issues included in their pre-election programs was focused on the prospects of the country's youngsters: "Dear children, be satisfied with one thing: we will definitely create all the conditions and opportunities for the realization of your abilities and talents from now on. I consider each of you, dear ones, my son, my daughter, my grandchild. I accept each of your achievements

and victories as my own. Always be worthy of such high trust and love of our dear Motherland, our hardworking people, my dear sons and daughters!" Shavkat Mirziyoyev said.

Based on the above points, it is possible to think that the fundamental stone of youngsters' education should be firmly laid in childhood. The role of the education and training process organized during the primary school period is particularly important in the comprehensive development and maturation of children. It is during this period that the cognitive processes and speech characteristics of primary school students appear as an accelerated stage. The development of speech in children of primary school age is in many ways related to the world around them and the quality of the organized educational and educational processes.

When children reach school age, their relation to each other relations acquire a new meaning. The child used to be parents, peers in the group, if they communicated with the teacher, now he communicates with the school teacher, the head of the class. In children a sense of responsibility is formed during this period.

On the eve of coming to school, the child's vocabulary increases to the extent that he can express his thoughts. If a normally developing child of this age uses 500-600 words in his speech, a six-year-old child uses 3000-7000 words. Children's speech of primary school age mainly consists of nouns, verbs, adjectives, numbers and conjunctions. Children of this age can distinguish which words are appropriate and which are not to be used in their speech. A 6-7-year-old child can compose sentences in a complex grammatical system. The child is whole in childhood, they acquire speech rapidly, and mastering speech becomes a specific activity. Another characteristic of 7-9-year-old children is that they not only express their thoughts in speech, but also know how to attract the attention of their interlocutor.

At preschool age, the child speaks without thinking, and in school, the language he speaks becomes a taught and learned science. In the process of reading and learning grammar, the phonetic aspect of the child's speech becomes correct, the syntactic structure of the speech improves. In the process of learning all the subjects taught at school, the vocabulary of the student's speech is enriched, the meaning of words deepens and expands for him. Children's acquisition of written speech is an important stage in the development of their speech. The child tries to express his thoughts in written speech. When the student performs written work according to the teacher's assignment, he knows in advance that his work will be evaluated based on the language in which he expresses his thoughts. A student

Practicing speaking to oneself while preparing an assignment at school has a great impact on the growth of speech. does.

The speech of the teacher plays a big role in the growth of children's speech.

because his speech is an example for students. That's why teacher should work on improving his speech.

It is the most actively used word for children at school amount increases. Mastery of written speech, reading and writing it is a qualification formed in life. Junior school age children's ability to form words by combining sounds after mastering, they sometimes misunderstand the content of the text. To him lack of students' vocabulary or distinguish the main idea not knowing. In this regard, the children are in front of the teacher increase vocabulary and learn independently about what they read there is a task of early teaching to make a plan. A child in writing lessons has great difficulty in writing letters and words. First a child focus on writing technique and sitting points. First, the child's written speech through his oral speech is determined, that is, he writes the word as he pronounces it. This regular exercises on vocalization with the child during the period transfer is important in his successful acquisition of spelling rules is important. Gestures and tone are not used in written speech.

Therefore, children's written speech is better than the oral speech of the teacher will be quite empty. Children's speech develops under the influence of adult speech. That's why pedagogues teach children verbally and teaching the culture of speech along with the development of written speech they need to go.

The main role model in the formation of speech culture in elementary school students is the teacher. The teacher's speech is thoroughly absorbed by the children. Therefore, it is necessary for the teacher to have the rules of speech and the culture of speaking beautifully, to be able to demonstrate the speech form of culture in his speech. Along with the speaking skills of the teacher, it is necessary to have the skills of forming children's speech skills and culture. Based on the formation of speech culture in primary school students, it is advisable to follow the following recommendations:

- organizing the correct use of words during the conversation;
- start a conversation in literary language;
- organizing the use of synonyms of words;
- promote not using profanity;
- promotion of book reading.

The above recommendations have a positive effect not only on the speech culture, but also on the psyche and behavior of a primary school student.

The process of formation of speech technique of elementary school students is also a process related to their mental state. Speech disorders are common in children of this age. For example:

- speak quickly;
- wrong breathing;
- stuttering in speech;
- to confuse words.

These speech disorders occur in elementary school students mainly as a result of two reasons, physiological and psychological effects.

One of the causes of speech disorders in elementary school students is the physiological feature that makes his voice capabilities invisible. A child's oral apparatus, which has a certain defect that is not fully formed, prevents him from speaking fluently. In this case, the teacher examines the child's capabilities by referring to a special specialist. If the student has a physiological defect, it causes permanent speech disorders

Causes of speech defects in elementary school students

Congenital defects in the physiological causal-speech apparatus, acquired defects.

Congenital defects in the physiological causal-speech apparatus, acquired defects

Manifestation of speech pronunciation deficits as a psychological phenomenon mainly occurs in elementary school students, who are physiologically healthy, when they speak in a hurry, when they are under strong excitement and stress. This situation needs to be eliminated on the basis of the teacher's skills. The teacher should teach the child the need to speak calmly and without haste.

Excitement, fear, and stress in speech disorders are mainly visible in classes led by a teacher with an authoritarian style. The fact that the teacher is too strict creates fear in the students, as a result, they cannot express what they know in speech, they make many mistakes. After understanding the speech manifested as a mental phenomenon in students, the teacher should follow the following when working with the student:

- to be kind to the child;
- adapting shy children to the environment by asking more questions;
- helping children prone to stress to deal with restraint and overcome their fears;
- influencing the child's psyche by praising and supporting him;
- practice to speak expressively without haste.

In short, speech is a complex process that reflects the unique culture of each nation. Therefore, it is the most urgent task to prepare the next generation, who is the mirror of our nation, the owners of beautiful, attractive and impressive speech. The author of "Nightmare" Kaikovus considered the skill of words - eloquence to be the best of all skills: "The skill of words is better than all the skills of knowledge" for no reason. It should not be forgotten that speech is a social phenomenon. So the speech culture of each person develops and educates the speech of other people.

REFERENCES

1. Isakhanova M. et al. THEORIES OF FOREIGN SCIENTISTS WHO SCIENTIFICALLY SHED LIGHT ON THE PSYCHOLOGICAL PROCESSES OF EARLY ADOLESCENCE //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 26. – С. 54-57
2. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?oi=bibs&hl=ru&cites=3377402382844567638&as_sdt=5
3. Исаханова, М. Э. "Психологические основы формирования критического мышления." Вестник по педагогике и психологии Южной Сибири 2 (2014): 102-108.
4. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?oi=bibs&hl=ru&q=related:tvVRC98_6o8J:scholar.google.com/
5. Исаханова, М. Э. (2015). Общение учителя. Наука. Мысль: электронный периодический журнал, (1), 7-12.
6. <https://scholar.google.com/scholar?oi=bibs&hl=ru&q=related:o4tx9puQQHwJ:scholar.google.com/>
7. Исаханова М. Культура речи учителя высшей школы //Ученый XXI века. – 2016. – №. 6-2 (19). – С. 45-48
8. <https://scholar.google.com/scholar?oi=bibs&hl=ru&q=related:aM4DffV6q9IJ:scholar.google.com/>
9. Исаханова, М. Э., & Ботирова, М. М. (2017). ОСНОВНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОГО МАСТЕРСТВА. Ученый XXI века, 75.
10. <https://scholar.google.com/scholar?oi=bibs&hl=ru&q=related:0A-n10AHbnAJ:scholar.google.com/>